

SKILLS ENSURING COACHING EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract: This article highlights the components and key elements of effective coaching skills. Interpersonal relationships are a set of relationships that develop between people in the form of feelings, judgments, and addressing each other. In the process of coaching, the main nine skills in interpersonal relations are: skills, leadership, effective communication, psychological safety and trust, emotional intellect, active listening, the ability to express (and receive) feedback, empathy, goal-oriented, sish idea is covered in detail.

Key words: skills, leadership, effective communication, psychological safety and confidence, emotional intellect, active listening, ability to give (and receive) feedback, empathy, goal-oriented, growth mindset, coaching, coaching, reflection, identification, paraphrase, echo - statement.

Admittedly, a good coach can change the game. However, a great coach can be life-changing. There's no denying that success alone won't lead to a team's top ranking unless it's provided with excellent coaching. Obviously, effective coaching is a way of developing self-confidence in others, regardless of the nature and environment of the team. Thus, a coach can turn human potential into high performance. A successful coach is always focused, supportive, observant, passionate, open communicator and goal oriented.

Effective coaches today must have nine key skills. Let's talk about them:

1. Leadership
2. Effective communication, communicativeness
3. Confidence
4. Emotional intelligence
5. Active listening
6. Ability to express (and receive) feedback
7. Empathy
8. Goal oriented
9. Growth mindset

1. Leadership

One of the most important skills a coach can develop is leadership. A good coach creates a sense of belonging in all team members. A coach builds a level of self-awareness in the individual to help them overcome their

unconscious and hidden biases. Ultimately, leadership skills help the coachee realize their potential and strengths.

Being responsible in the workplace is not only good for the leader, but also gives very positive feelings for the employee. Because job satisfaction is very important for health.

BetterUp Labs found that employees are 50% more productive, 90% more innovative, and 150% more engaged. Leadership also reduces employee turnover by 54%.

2. Effective communication, communicativeness is considered the main working tool of this class. In our country, it is not said that if your work is in vain, your hard work will be less. One of the most essential effective coaching skills is communication. A great coach must have excellent communication skills. They have invested in building relationships with clients as part of their coaching approach. They must have acquired the ability to use effective communication as part of their coaching technique.

For many great coaches, communication is the foundation of any successful coaching relationship. Effective communication provides an opportunity to clearly define the direction of coaching, goals and methods, techniques and conditions. A warm sociable atmosphere clearly defines the event of future work.

3. trust and psychological safety.

A coaching relationship is based on trust. Let's face it: coaching involves very complex processes. Sometimes a coach gives advice, feedback, or instructions that you don't want to hear. It can be uncomfortable and unpleasant at the same time. But that's why building trust is so important for coaches. For coaching to be effective, the coach must have the trust of the clients.

4. Emotional intelligence.

Although it may seem counter-intuitive to the coaching process, emotional intelligence is critical. Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand emotions. People with high levels of emotional intelligence understand how emotions and feelings influence thoughts, behaviors, and actions.

Thus, emotional intelligence is essential for coaches and leaders to understand how team members feel about a particular decision, process or project. In many ways, emotional intelligence helps coaches and leaders become better at solving problems within teams. Ultimately, these skills help team members and prevent problems from occurring in the first place.

5. Active listening.

Any good coach relies on active listening in problem solving. Listening skills help coaches and leaders assess the situation at hand. Listening helps the coachee observe and understand the problem and better understand how to find a solution. But most importantly, listening helps the coach ask the right open-ended questions.

Most of the listening is done in questions. By applying active listening skills, a leader can identify misaligned priorities. By asking good questions, team members will better find out where to focus to build relationships.

6. The ability to express (and receive) feedback.

One of the key coaching skills for long-term behavior change is the art of feedback. But everyone knows that expressing an opinion is not an easy task. It can be awkward - and it takes a good amount of practice.

But feedback is often a factor in learning the views and attitudes of team members. Feedback is a two-way street.

7. Empathy.

Healthy empathy is formed in effective coaching. We know that now more than ever, team members are fully committed to their work. This sense of seeing a team member as a whole requires a deeper level of empathy. Coaches must recognize their clients as human beings. They need to understand what is happening in their personal life and at work. After all, a person's personality levels affect how they manifest themselves at work.

8. Goal orientation.

Every action of an effective coach must be carefully thought out and aimed at a specific goal. In order to move to the next stage, the goal must be clear and activities must be planned. If the coach does not have a road map for the personal and professional development of the client in front of him, uncertainty and subsequent actions will not result.

9. Growth mindset. Finally, it is important for every good coach to have a growth mindset. Because if the coach does not work on himself regularly, his work efficiency will decrease. Each coach has the opportunity to improve his personal and professional qualities with various methods and techniques. Only desire, strong will and responsibility are required for this.

We found it necessary to dwell on the features of active listening.

Active listening is a technique and at the same time a process of maximum concentration on the other person in which all subtleties and nuances during the conversation should be taken into account: voice, intonation, facial

expressions, gestures and sudden stops. The main components of the active listening method are:

1. Neutrality. Avoiding judgment, criticism and accusations. Accepting and respecting a person.

2. Good intention. The attitude towards the interlocutor and the interlocutor, encouraging him to continue talking about himself, contributes to the problem - trust.

3. Sincere interest. One of the most important means of influencing the method of active listening is that it helps the person to open up more and identify the problem situation.

Active listening techniques

The method of active listening is multi-functional and diverse, there are five main methods of active listening:

1. A pause. It is important for a person to speak to the end and pause in the conversation. This does not mean that you have to be silent all the time: *poddakivanie* ("yes", "hugo"), a nod is a signal for the person who heard them.

2. Agreement. For unclear points, clarifying questions ask questions to speculate on the situation and better understand the interlocutor or client.

3. Paraphrase. The heard speaker is written in a short form, allowing the interlocutor to confirm "yes, everything is like that", or to clarify and clarify important issues.

4. Exo-statement (repetition) - "returning" to the interlocutor in an unchanged form - a person understands that he was listened to carefully (not to abuse this conversation in the conversation).

5. Reflecting feelings. Expressions are used that correspond to a person's experience: "You are angry ...", "It was very sad for you at that time G' was happy."

Rules for active listening

The principles of active listening consist of important components without which this method will not work:

- it is impossible to stop the interlocutor;
- the asked question answers the answer, does not help to answer or answer, the interlocutor himself must answer this question - it is necessary to interrupt;
- important information: support;

when a person hides aggressive and negative emotions, it is necessary to listen to them until they stop.

Interview method. This method helps in the process of pedagogical observation to obtain complete information, to make a correct assessment of the current situation, to create pedagogical conditions that allow to find a solution to the problem, and to solve the problem of the possibilities of the subjects of experimental - test work.

The conversation can be individual, group and public, depending on the purpose

is fired. During the interview, the possibilities of the respondents are fully revealed

it is important to achieve.

The interview method is the problem being researched by the coach or provides a response to the event that illuminates this aspect. The interview is conducted on the basis of referring a series of questions to the attention of the respondent. The reaction of the researcher to the questions received during the interview increases its effectiveness.

The idea of another person is closely related to the level of self-awareness. The analysis of self-awareness through another person is carried out using two concepts: identification and reflection.

Identification is one of the mechanisms of human cognition and understanding, which consists in unconsciously simulating oneself with another important person.

Another important person here is an authorized person for a specific communication and activity subject. This usually happens in real situations of interaction, when a person tries to put himself in the place of the communication partner. During identification, a certain emotional connection with the object is established.

It is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of "identification" and "reflection". If the basis for the first concept is the process of assimilation of the subject to the communication partner, that is, to the significant other, then the main thing for the second concept ("reference") is the subject's dependence on other people. acts as a selective attitude towards them. The object of a referential relationship can be a group of which the subject is a member, or another group to which he associates himself without actually being a member. The function of a reference object can be performed by a separate person, including those who do not exist in reality (a literary character, a fantastic ideal for imitation, etc.). In both cases, the subject receives for himself the goals,

values, ideas, norms and rules of behavior of the appropriate object (group, individual).

The concept of "identification" is close to the concept of "empathy" according to its content. Empathy - understanding the emotional state of a person in the form of empathy. The mechanism of empathy is similar to the mechanism of identification.

This similarity lies in the ability to put oneself in the place of another, to look at things from his point of view. However, this does not mean impersonation (as in identification). Simply empathy takes into account the behavior of the partner, the subject treats him with sympathy, but interpersonal relations with him are built on the basis of his behavioral strategy.

Reflection is a person's knowledge of how he is perceived by his communication partner, that is, how others understand him. In the process of interaction, certain characteristics of each other are mutually evaluated and changed. These are very important in coaching.

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